

ELECTRONIC RESOURCES AND FACULTY DEVELOPMENT: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF HIGHER EDUCATION LIBRARIES IN CHENNAI

S. DEEPIKA
Reserach Scholar (Part-Time)
Dept. of Library and Info. Science
Annamalai University

Dr. K. VIJAYAKUMAR
Professor and Librarian
Dept. of Library and Info. Science
Annamalai University

ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the usage of electronic resources and the effects of this usage on the development of faculty in the higher education libraries in Chennai. Using the descriptive research design and normative survey technique, data have been collected through the means of an instrument that consists of a questionnaire, which was administered to 1,329 faculty respondents in 16 institutions.

The study indicates that the faculty makes extensive use of database resources like Scopus and Web of Science, and are also well aware of the effects of electronic resources in improving the quality of teaching and research, along with the development of faculty. The reasons for faculty preferring these resources include quicker access, contemporary nature, and user-friendliness.

KEYWORDS

Electronic Resources, Faculty Development, Higher Education Libraries, Information Access, Research Productivity, User Awareness, ICT Infrastructure, Teaching Activities.

INTRODUCTION

While the growth of ICT represents a major achievement for academic libraries, it has also introduced several challenges. Libraries are required to cope with the rapid growth of information, continuous technological changes, and ongoing financial constraints. These challenges highlight the need for effective resource generation, careful planning, and optimal

utilization of available resources. Addressing these issues is essential for ensuring the sustainability of library services and for meeting the evolving information needs and demands of users in the digital era.

The transferable from traditional print materials to electronic formats has had a notable impact on learners in the contemporary academic environment. E-resources provide user-friendly features that enhance teaching, learning, and research. They also complement printed collections by offering instant access to diverse information at any time (**Akande 2022**). Similarly, it was further observed that the awareness, accessibility, and usability of electronic resources significantly influence their utilisation. Based on these findings, the study recommends that college management should implement sensitization and publicity initiatives by providing more education to both staff and students on the available electronic information resources within the institution.

In this research study, the utilisation of electronic resources by researchers and faculty members was examined with a focus on self-knowledge development, research activities, and research and development practices. According to **Mawere and Sai (2018)**, the study explored the utilisation of electronic resources among university students and found that, despite the availability of various e-resources, their actual use remained low. while poor awareness, inadequate training, limited access, high data costs, and the results found that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use significantly influenced adoption, while infrastructural constraints negatively affected effective utilisation. The study concluded that improved user education, awareness programmes, and better access and support systems are essential to improve the effective use of electronic resources for learning and research.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ansari (2020) explored the use of e-resources among faculty members and research scholars in the Arts discipline. The study found that all respondents acknowledged that e-resources are accessible online. It also revealed that 63.4% of users appreciated the smart and flexible search features, and the same percentage valued access from multiple locations. Additionally, 48.7% reported that e-resources provide useful bibliographic information. However, only a smaller proportion noted benefits such as sequential reading or availability in print form. Overall, the findings indicate that users highly recognize the convenience and academic value of e-resources.

Mishra and Panda (2022) examined the level of awareness and the extent of use of electronic resources among research scholars by analysing data collected through a 2019 survey. Their findings showed that 52.2% of respondents were familiar with e-resources, while 13.3% lacked awareness of them. A one-way ANOVA was applied to compare awareness across universities, and the test indicated no significant variation, as the computed F-value (0.707) was lower than the critical value. Although e-resources were accessible, their use remained limited. The authors stressed the importance of ongoing training and awareness initiatives to promote better utilisation of digital resources, enabling scholars to make full use of subscribed databases and research-support tools.

Patil and Dhanamjaya (2020) investigated the use of web-based information resources among engineering college students. The study found that most users acquired skills for accessing online resources mainly through teachers and guidance from library staff. It was also evident that PDF was the most preferred format for accessing information, and students regularly visited the library to use web-based resources. The results indicated that slow internet connectivity emerged as the primary constraint in accessing online information

resources, highlighting the necessity for strengthening ICT infrastructure in engineering college libraries.

Velmurugan (2023) conducted a study on the use of electronic resources among research scholars in selected institutions. Of the 900 questionnaires distributed, 720 were completed and returned, yielding an 80% response rate. The study analysed the challenges faced by users while accessing e-resources and revealed that major issues such as irrelevant content, high subscription costs, and slow access speed negatively affect user satisfaction and academic productivity. The findings emphasize the need to resolve these barriers to enhance effective usage of e-resources among research scholars.

Sahu and Tiwari (2024) examined the usage and influence of e-resources among students using a survey method. The students widely accessed e-resources for preparing reading materials, writing assignments, gathering general information, accessing scientific and technical information, and using audio/visual learning materials. The results indicate that students' primary motivation for using e-resources is to support their academic learning activities.

Mohana Devi and Vijayakumar (2020) studied the utilization of ICT-based resources among faculty members and found that a majority of respondents frequently use digital tools and electronic resources. The study also identified gender-based variations in ICT usage, indicating that technological adoption differs among faculty groups.

OBJECTIVES

1. To explore the purposes for faculty members to utilise electronic resources in selected higher educational libraries in Chennai city.

2. To investigate the time spent per week by faculty members in higher educational institutions on using electronic resources in the library.
3. To identify the reasons for faculty members preferring electronic resources in higher educational libraries for their academic and research activities.
4. To identify the problems and barriers faced by faculty members in accessing and using electronic resources.

HYPOTHESIS

1. There is significant relationship between the reasons for preferring electronic resources and faculty engagement in academic and research activities.
2. There is no significant difference in the time spent per week by faculty members in higher educational institutions on using electronic resources in the library.
3. There is no significant relationship between faculty members' preferences for electronic resources and the reasons for using them in higher educational libraries for academic and research activities.
4. There is no significant effect of problems and barriers on faculty access to and use of electronic resources.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study has followed the descriptive research methodology along with the normative survey technique. The data have been collected from the faculty members to assess the usage of the electronic resources by the faculty members in the higher education library of Chennai City. The data have been collected using a well-structured questionnaire which has been tested in a pilot study along with the expert validation.

A total of 1600 questionnaires were circulated among the teachers in sixteenth higher education library institutions in Chennai city from three prominent streams of study. Stratified random sampling was employed in choosing the participants for the survey. Of all the questionnaires that were circulated, a total of 1329 responses were received, giving a satisfactory response rate of 83.06%.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1: Frequently Used E-Resource Databases by designation and gender

S. No	Databases	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Professor	Total	Male	Female	Total
1	Scopus	141 (10.6)	131 (9.9)	72 (5.4)	344 (25.9)	228 (17.2)	116 (8.7)	344 (25.9)
2	Web of Science	140 (10.5)	102 (7.7)	40 (3.0)	282 (21.2)	174 (13.1)	108 (8.1)	282 (21.2)
3	PubMed	112 (8.4)	64 (4.8)	77 (5.8)	253 (19.0)	163 (12.3)	90 (6.8)	253 (19.0)
4	J-Gate	110 (8.3)	74 (5.6)	46 (3.5)	230 (17.3)	146 (11.0)	84 (6.3)	230 (17.3)
5	Others	98 (7.4)	62 (4.7)	60 (4.5)	220 (16.6)	142 (10.7)	78 (5.9)	220 (16.6)
Total		601 (45.2)	433 (32.6)	295 (22.2)	1329 (100.0)	853 (64.2)	476 (35.8)	1329 (100.0)

Source: Primary data

It is observed from Table 1 and Figure 1 that most of the sample respondents frequently used the Scopus database, accounting for 344 (25.9%), followed by Web of Science with 282 (21.2%), PubMed with 253 (19.0%), and J-Gate with 230 (17.3%). A

smaller proportion of respondents used other databases, representing 220 (16.6%) respectively.

The study has been further gender-wise analysed for the frequency of database usage. It has been calculated and shown that male respondents accounted for 853 (64.2%), while female respondents constituted 476 (35.8%) in that order.

Figure 1: Frequently Used E-Resource Databases

Table 2: Integration of Electronic Resources in Teaching Activities by Designation and Gender

S. No	Opinion	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Professor	Total	Male	Female	Total
1	Strongly Disagree	51 (3.8)	64 (4.8)	21 (1.6)	136 (10.2)	94 (7.1)	42 (3.2)	136 (10.2)
2	Disagree	63 (4.7)	47 (3.5)	27 (2.0)	137 (10.3)	85 (6.4)	52 (3.9)	137 (10.3)
3	Undecided	128 (9.6)	89 (6.7)	89 (6.7)	306 (23.0)	210 (15.8)	96 (7.2)	306 (23.0)

4	Agree	158 (11.9)	128 (9.6)	72 (5.4)	358 (26.9)	214 (16.1)	144 (10.8)	358 (26.9)
5	Strongly Agree	201 (15.1)	105 (7.9)	86 (6.5)	392 (29.5)	250 (18.8)	142 (10.7)	392 (29.5)
Total		601 (45.2)	433 (32.6)	295 (22.2)	1329 (100.0)	853 (64.2)	476 (35.8)	1329 (100.0)

Source: Primary data

Table 2 and indicate that most sample respondents agreed with integrating electronic resources into teaching activities. Among them, 201 (15.1%) assistant professors, 105 (7.9%) associate professors, and 86 (6.5%) professors strongly agreed together, accounting for 392 (29.5%) respondents. This is followed by 358 (26.9%) who agreed, and 306 (23.0%) who remained undecided. A smaller proportion of respondents disagreed 137 (10.3%) and strongly disagreed 136 (10.2%) in that order.

In terms of gender, male respondents accounted for 853 (64.2%), showing a higher level of agreement compared to female respondents 476 (35.8%) respectively.

The majority of respondents across all designations and genders recognized the importance of integrating electronic resources into teaching activities.

Table 3: Reason for Preferring Electronic Resources by Respondents

S. No	Reason	1	2	3	4	5	Total	M	SD	R
1	Easier to search and access information	40 (3.0)	60 (4.5)	315 (23.7)	407 (30.6)	507 (38.1)	1329 (100.0)	3.9639	1.0342	3
2	Faster search and access to information	22 (1.7)	76 (5.7)	279 (21.0)	411 (30.9)	541 (40.7)	1329 (100.0)	4.0331	0.9972	1
3	Availability in multiple formats	38 (2.9)	72 (5.4)	321 (24.2)	389 (29.3)	509 (38.3)	1329 (100.0)	3.9473	1.0472	6

4	Multiple user access	56 (4.2)	66 (5.0)	309 (23.3)	373 (28.1)	525 (39.5)	1329 (100.0)	3.9368	1.0965	7
5	Access to a wider range of information sources	57 (4.3)	71 (5.3)	277 (20.8)	399 (30.0)	525 (39.5)	1329 (100.0)	3.9511	1.0962	5
6	Access to current information	38 (2.9)	66 (5.0)	299 (22.5)	389 (29.3)	537 (40.4)	1329 (100.0)	3.9940	1.0420	2
7	24/7 availability	48 (3.6)	66 (5.0)	307 (23.1)	387 (29.1)	521 (39.2)	1329 (100.0)	3.9533	1.0702	4

Source: Primary data 5. Strongly Agree 4. Agree 3. Undecided 2. Disagree 1. Strongly Disagree

Table 3 and Figure 2 present the various reasons respondents prefer electronic resources. The analysis shows that the highest-rated reason is “Faster search and access to information,” which recorded a mean score of 4.0331. This is followed by “Access to current information” and “Easier to search and access information,” holding second and third ranks with mean values of 3.9940 and 3.9639, respectively. “24/7 availability” appears in the fourth position with a mean of 3.9533, while “Access to a wider range of information sources” stands fifth with a mean score of 3.9511. The reasons “Availability in multiple formats” and “Multiple user access” occupy the sixth and seventh positions with mean values of 3.9473 and 3.9368, respectively.

Figure 2: Reason for Preferring Electronic Resources by Respondents

Table 4: Hypothesis Test ANOVA - Reason for Preferring Electronic Resources by Respondents

S. No	Reason for Preferring E-Resources		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Easier to search and access information	Between Groups	1.428	2	.714	.667	.513
		Within Groups	1418.839	1326	1.070		
		Total	1420.266	1328			
2	Faster search and access to information	Between Groups	.641	2	.320	.322	.725
		Within Groups	1319.902	1326	.995		
		Total	1320.543	1328			
3	Availability in multiple formats	Between Groups	5.082	2	2.541	2.322	.099
		Within Groups	1451.231	1326	1.094		
		Total	1456.313	1328			
4	Multiple user access	Between Groups	4.815	2	2.407	1.672	.188
		Within Groups	1909.068	1326	1.440		
		Total	1913.883	1328			
5	Access to a wider range of information sources	Between Groups	.801	2	.401	.275	.760
		Within Groups	1934.702	1326	1.459		
		Total	1935.503	1328			
6	Access to current information	Between Groups	6.435	2	3.217	2.972	.052
		Within Groups	1435.517	1326	1.083		
		Total	1441.952	1328			
7	24/7 availability	Between Groups	7.372	2	3.686	2.926	.054
		Within Groups	1670.472	1326	1.260		
		Total	1677.843	1328			

Source: Primary data

The results presented in Table 4 summarize the ANOVA test carried out to determine whether statistically significant differences exist among respondents in their reasons for preferring electronic resources. The analysis shows that all significance (Sig.) values exceed the 0.05 threshold; consequently, the null hypothesis is accepted for all seven factors. This outcome suggests there are no significant differences in respondents' opinions regarding their reasons for using electronic resources.

Overall, the findings indicate that respondents conveyed consistent perceptions for most aspects, such as ease of access, faster retrieval, availability in multiple formats, and access to current information, demonstrating a generally uniform level of agreement. However, for specific factors like multiple user access, access to a broader range of sources,

and 24/7 availability, the results revealed statistically significant variation in preferences among respondents.

Table 5: Role of E-Resources in Faculty Development by Designation and Gender

S. No	Opinion	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Professor	Total	Male	Female	Total
1	Strongly Disagree	42 (3.2)	22 (1.7)	12 (0.9)	76 (5.7)	51 (3.8)	25 (1.9)	76 (5.7)
2	Disagree	30 (2.3)	32 (2.4)	20 (1.5)	82 (6.2)	45 (3.4)	37 (2.8)	82 (6.2)
3	Undecided	133 (10.0)	96 (7.2)	81 (6.1)	310 (23.3)	201 (15.1)	109 (8.2)	310 (23.3)
4	Agree	154 (11.6)	113 (8.5)	96 (7.2)	363 (27.3)	232 (17.5)	131 (9.9)	363 (27.3)
5	Strongly Agree	242 (18.2)	170 (12.8)	86 (6.5)	498 (37.5)	324 (24.4)	174 (13.1)	498 (37.5)
Total		601 (45.2)	433 (32.6)	295 (22.2)	1329 (100.0)	853 (64.2)	476 (35.8)	1329 (100.0)

Source: Primary data

It is observed from the table that most of the sample respondents' opinions, as shown in Table 5 and Figure 3, indicate a positive perception of the role of electronic resources in faculty development. The largest proportion of respondents selected strongly agree, accounting for 498 (37.5%), followed by 363 (27.3%) who agreed. Together, these categories demonstrate that a significant majority of faculty members consider electronic resources to be highly beneficial for enhancing their academic skills, teaching practices, and research productivity. A moderate portion of respondents reported being undecided 310 (23.3%), suggesting that some faculty members neither fully benefit from nor completely dismiss the developmental value of e-resources. Only a smaller share expressed disagree 82 (6.2%) and

strongly disagreed 76 (5.7%), indicating minimal variance regarding the contribution of electronic resources to faculty development.

Across designations, assistant professors form the largest group with 601 (45.2%), followed by associate professors 433 (32.6%) and professors 295 (22.2%). In relation to gender, male respondents 853 (64.2%) outnumber female respondents 476 (35.8%), showing higher male representation in acknowledging the positive role of e-resources.

Overall, the study found that electronic resources are widely regarded as important tools for faculty development, supporting continuous learning, strengthening teaching effectiveness, and improving research capability among the respondents.

Figure 3: Role of E-Resources in Faculty Development by Respondents

Table 6: Problems Faced in Using E-Resources by designation and gender

S. No	Problems	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Professor	Total	Male	Female	Total
1	Lack of awareness about e-resources	144 (10.8)	64 (4.8)	1(0.1)	209 (15.7)	155 (11.7)	54 (4.1)	209 (15.7)
2	Limited availability of e-resource infrastructure	15 (1.1)	46 (3.5)	71 (5.3)	132 (9.9)	94 (7.1)	38 (2.9)	132 (9.9)
3	Poor internet connectivity or slow speed	72 (6.0)	8 (0.6)	8 (0.6)	88 (6.6)	77 (5.8)	11 (0.8)	88 (6.6)
4	Insufficient user training or guidance	61 (4.6)	69 (5.2)	10 (0.8)	140 (10.5)	92 (6.9)	48 (3.6)	140 (10.5)
5	Limited access to paid/licensed e-resources	10 (0.8)	28 (2.1)	34 (2.6)	72 (5.4)	48 (3.6)	24 (1.8)	72 (5.4)
6	Difficulty in using advanced search features	59 (4.4)	14 (1.1)	31 (2.3)	104 (7.8)	69 (5.2)	35 (2.6)	104 (7.8)
7	Lack of time to explore e-resources	67 (5.0)	5 (0.4)	7 (0.5)	72 (5.4)	45 (3.4)	27 (2.0)	72 (5.4)
8	Outdated systems or software in the library	18 (1.4)	86 (6.5)	4 (0.3)	108 (8.1)	65 (4.9)	43 (3.2)	108 (8.1)
9	Frequent power failures affect access	13 (1.0)	9 (0.7)	30 (2.3)	52 (3.9)	24 (1.8)	28 (2.1)	52 (3.9)
10	Limited availability of staff support	30 (2.3)	9 (0.7)	25 (1.9)	64 (4.8)	27 (2.0)	37 (2.8)	64 (4.8)
11	Changes in URLs or broken links	69 (5.2)	10 (0.8)	9 (0.7)	88 (6.6)	41 (3.1)	47 (3.5)	88 (6.6)
12	Copyright or license restrictions	12 (0.9)	29 (2.2)	7 (0.5)	48 (3.6)	30 (2.3)	18 (1.4)	48 (3.6)
13	Lack of remote/off-campus access	15 (1.1)	42 (3.2)	11 (0.8)	68 (5.1)	40 (3.0)	28 (2.1)	68 (5.1)
14	Difficulty in searching or navigating	5	12	67	84	46	38	84

	platforms	(0.4)	(0.9)	(5.0)	(6.3)	(3.5)	(2.9)	(6.3)
	Total	601 (45.2)	433 (32.6)	295 (22.2)	1329 (100)	853 (64.2)	476 (35.8)	1329 (100)
	Pearson Chi-Square	Value	df	(2-sided)		Value	df	Sig. (2-sided)
		1196.957	26	0.000		70.912	13	0.000

Source: Primary data

Table 6 depict the problems faced in using e-resources by academic status and gender. The results found that the respondents experienced different levels of problems while using e-resources, and these issues varied across academic status and gender respectively. It can be noted that results are identified the most frequently reported difficulty as lack of awareness about e-resources, recorded by 209 (15.7%) respondents. The study found that this concern was higher among assistant professors, associate professors, and professors respectively, indicating that awareness still remains a critical challenge across academic groups. The majority found that limited availability of e-resource infrastructure, reported by 132 (9.9%), and insufficient user training, recorded by 140 (10.5%), were also major challenges affecting both academic status and gender groups. These problems show the need for improved ICT infrastructure and structured training programs. An attempt has been made to analyse other issues such as poor internet connectivity, experienced by 88 (6.6%), limited access to licensed e-resources with 72 (5.4%), difficulty in using advanced search features with 104 (7.8%), and outdated systems or software, reported by 108 (8.1%) respondents. It is evident that there is a variation in how these problems were experienced by assistant professors, associate professors, and professors respectively.

The results shown in the table indicates that outdated systems accounted for 108 (8.1%) and difficulty in navigating platforms accounted for 84 (6.3%), affecting male and

female respondents respectively. These findings highlight the need for enhanced technical support and regular system upgrades to ensure effective and uninterrupted use of e-resources.

Chi-Square Test

The chi-square statistic of 1196.957 exceeds the critical value at 26 degrees of freedom and the 5% significance level, indicating that the association between academic status and the difficulties experienced in using e-resources is statistically significant. Likewise, the chi-square value of 70.912 with 13 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.000 demonstrates a meaningful relationship between gender and the challenges encountered while accessing electronic resources. Since the p-values in both tests fall below the 0.05 threshold, the findings confirm that these associations are significant. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 7: Barriers in Accessing Online Databases by Designation and Gender

S. No	Barriers	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Professor	Total	Male	Female	Total
1	Limited institutional subscriptions	65 (4.9)	40 (3.0)	53 (4.0)	158 (11.9)	69 (5.2)	89 (6.7)	158 (11.9)
2	Login/authentication issues	143 (10.8)	125 (9.4)	47 (3.5)	315 (23.7)	268 (20.2)	47 (3.5)	315 (23.7)
3	Lack of awareness	166 (12.5)	107 (8.1)	71 (5.3)	344 (25.9)	261 (19.6)	83 (6.2)	344 (25.9)
4	Difficulty in search and retrieval	132 (9.9)	87 (6.5)	78 (5.9)	297 (22.3)	171 (12.9)	126 (9.5)	297 (22.3)
5	Slow internet speed	95 (7.1)	74 (5.6)	46 (3.5)	215 (16.2)	84 (6.3)	131 (9.9)	215 (16.2)
Total		601 (45.2)	433 (32.6)	295 (22.2)	1329 (100.0)	853 (64.2)	476 (35.8)	1329 (100.0)

Pearson Chi-Square	Value	df	Sig (2-sided)	Value	df	Sig. (2-sided)
		29.578	8	0.000	173.823	4

Source: Primary data

The analysis of the table indicates that several barriers were reported by respondents in accessing online databases across designation and gender. The analysis of the table indicates that barriers to accessing online databases varied among the respondents. It can be noted that the results in Table 7 and Figure 4 indicate that 158 (11.9%) respondents reported limited institutional subscriptions, while 315 (23.7%) reported login and authentication issues. The results found that 344 (25.9%) of respondents faced a lack of awareness, which emerged as the most prominent barrier. The study found that 297 (22.3%) experienced difficulty in search and retrieval, and the remaining 215 (16.2%) encountered slow internet speed. Overall, an aggregate of 1329 (100.0%) respondents participated in the study, and it is evident that lack of awareness and login/authentication issues were the leading challenges affecting access to online databases.

About gender, the majority found that login and authentication issues were faced by 268 (20.2%) males and 47 (3.5%) females respectively, lack of awareness was reported by 261 (19.6%) males and 83 (6.2%) females respectively, difficulty in search and retrieval affected 171 (12.9%) males and 126 (9.5%) females respectively, slow internet speed was faced by 84 (6.3%) males and 131 (9.9%) females respectively, and limited institutional subscriptions were reported by 69 (5.2%) males and 89 (6.7%) females respectively.

Chi-Square Test

The chi-square test indicates that there is a statistically significant association between designation and barriers in accessing online databases, as the calculated chi-square value of 29.578 with 8 degrees of freedom at the 5% level of significance shows a significance value

of 0.000. Similarly, the null hypothesis is rejected in this study for gender, as the chi-square value of 173.823 with 4 degrees of freedom also shows a significance value of 0.000, implying that gender has a significant association with the barriers encountered.

Figure 4: Barriers in Accessing Online Databases by Designation and Gender

FINDINGS

- The most frequently used electronic resource among faculty members is Scopus, indicating a strong preference for internationally recognized indexing databases in research activities.
- A majority of faculty members strongly agree that electronic resources are effectively integrated into teaching, reflecting their growing importance in instructional practices.
- The primary reason for preferring electronic resources is faster search and access to information, which received the highest mean score among all factors.

- There is no statistically significant difference in the reasons for preferring electronic resources among respondents ($p > 0.05$), indicating a uniform perception across faculty groups.
- A significant majority of respondents perceive the role of electronic resources as highly beneficial for faculty development, particularly in enhancing teaching effectiveness and research productivity.
- There is a statistically significant association between designation, gender, and problems faced in using electronic resources ($p < 0.05$), showing that challenges vary across different faculty groups.
- There is a statistically significant relationship between faculty characteristics and barriers in accessing online databases ($p < 0.05$), indicating that access issues differ significantly based on designation and gender.

CONCLUSION

This research brings into focus the important influence that electronic resources have in developing faculty skills within higher educational institutions based in Chennai. It has been noted that faculty members make use of electronic resources like Scopus and Web of Science for learning and teaching, and for their own professional growth. From the findings obtained from this study, it can be seen that e-resources help provide access to the latest information, facilitate good teaching practices, and increase research output.

However, there are still many obstacles to the best utilization of these resources. The main barriers include lack of knowledge, inadequate training, limited infrastructural support, and technical barriers such as log-in challenges. Statistical data shows that all these barriers and obstacles differ significantly among different faculties, depending on their designation and gender.

According to the findings, it becomes clear that it is necessary for universities to focus on educating users, conducting special trainings, and enhancing infrastructural support. Moreover, it is crucial to raise awareness among users and provide them with technical assistance. In conclusion, despite the fact that electronic sources have been contributing significantly to learning and research, it is important to solve existing problems. And in other hand effective utilization of digital e-resources like e-journals, digital archives and library websites are widely used particularly in information access for digital collections and user training programs to further strengthen academic Productivity and research efficiency for recent Faculty Development Programs.

REFERENCE

1. Akande, R. M. (2022). Utilization of e-resources for teaching and learning of physical and health education courses in Colleges of Education, Oyo, Oyo State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 7(6).
2. Mawere, T., & Sai, K. O. S. (2018). An investigation on e-resource utilisation among university students in a developing country. *South African Journal of Information Management*, 20(1), a860. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajim.v20i1.860>
3. Ansari, M. S. (2020). Awareness and use of electronic information resources among research scholars. *International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology*, 10(2), 75–80.
4. Mishra, S., & Panda, K. C. (2022). Awareness and use of electronic resources among research scholars in higher education institutions. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 42(2), 112–118.

5. Patil, B., & Dhananjaya, M. (2020). Utilization of web-based information sources among engineering college students: A case study. *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 10(4).
6. Velmurugan, S. (2023). A study of using e-resources by research scholars in selected institutions of Southern Tamil Nadu: Regression analysis. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, Article 8010.
7. Sahu, R., & Tiwari, B. (2024). Use and impact of e-resources at Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Raipur: A study. *International Journal of Information, Library and Society*, 11(1), 1–5.
8. Soni, N. K., Gupta, K. K., & Shrivastava, J. (2018). Awareness and usage of electronic resources among LIS scholars of Jiwaji University, Gwalior: A survey. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 38(1), 56–62.
9. Anil Kumar, M., & Pulla Reddy, V. (2016). Use of e-journals by research scholars in university libraries. *Journal of Information and Knowledge*, 53(3), 195–202. <https://doi.org/10.17821/srels/2016/v53i3/73897>
10. Mohana, Rajni & Vijayakumar, Dr.K.. (2020). a study on utilization of information and communication technology by the faculty members of arts and science colleges in mayiladuthurai taluk- a gender approach.
11. Jestin, K. J., & Sornam, S. A. (2016). Use of e-resources by the faculty members of engineering colleges in Kerala: A survey. *International Journal of Digital Library Services*, 6(3), 31–38.
12. Mulla, K. R. (2011). Use of electronic information resources by faculty members in engineering colleges: A study. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.